

**STUDENT-SUPERVISOR RELATIONSHIP AND ACADEMIC STAFF'S STRIKE ACTION AS
DETERMINANTS OF TIMELY COMPLETION IN POSTGRADUATE EDUCATIONAL
MANAGEMENT PROGRAMME IN UNIVERSITIES IN NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated how student-supervisor relationship and ASUU's strike action determine timely completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme (PGEMP) in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. Three research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study employed a descriptive survey research design to guide the study. The population for the study was 296 respondents (21 PGEMP lecturers and 275 PGEMP students) from the study area. The sample for this study 296, which was selected using census sampling. A structured questionnaire titled: "Postgraduate Educational Management Programme Variable (PEMPVQ)" and a checklist titled "PGEMP Completion Rate" were used as the data collection instruments. PEMPVQ was validated and pilot tested through Cronbach Alpha, which revealed a reliability co-efficient of 0.81. At the end of the data collection exercise, 283 valid questionnaires were retrieved, which represented 95.6% of the total questionnaires administered. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while linear regression was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study showed that students-supervisor relationship ($F(1, 281) = 11.902, p < 0.05$) and ASUU strikes ($F(1, 281) = 7.494, p < 0.05$) significantly determines students' timely completion in PGEMP in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that student-supervisor relationship and ASUU's strike action significantly determine timely completion in PGEMP in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. Hence, the study recommends amongst others that PGEMP supervisors should facilitate meaningful interactions and communication between students and themselves, which can provide opportunities for regular thesis feedback, and support to enhance the quality of supervision.

Keywords: Student-Supervisor Relationship, ASUU Strike, Postgraduate Educational Management Programme

INTRODUCTION

Timely completion generally refers to the percentage of students that finish postgraduate (PG) programme within the anticipated time period. Hence, it is an academic indicator which provides information on how well an institution is serving its students and the extent to which students complete postgraduate programme based on certain factors. Such factors according to Koko (2015); Olorunisola (2015); Yaya (2019); Gbesoevi (2021) may include a programme's admission, administrative procedure, supervisory, environmental, field, and style of study policies may affect postgraduate students' timely completion. Also, Amugo, Zakari and Lulu-Pokubo (2018) identify the non-conformity with postgraduate academic

calendar, funding, incessant ASUU strike and staffing policy as other factors that determine timely completion in postgraduate programmes. In same vein, Mbogo (2016); Hadi and Muhammad (2019); Badau (2020) attributes timely completion to the students' attitude, relationship with supervisors, socio-economic status and research competence. Hence, student-supervisor relationship and Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU)'s incessant strike actions were identified and discussed in this study as determinants of postgraduate students' timely completion.

Students-supervisor relationship according to Rugut (2017), refers to the collaborative partnership between a student and supervisor(s) who provide guidance, support, and mentorship throughout the student's research or academic project. The supervisor is typically an academic faculty member who has expertise in a postgraduate student's field of study and provides advice on the research design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation of the results (Litalien, 2015). The supervisor plays a crucial role in guiding and supporting the student's research work, providing feedback, and ensuring that the research work meets the required standard. It is important that students understand the responsibilities, supervisors have so that they have clear expectations as to what the supervisory team is and what its purpose (Fragouli, 2021). The relationship between the supervisor and the student can impact the quality and timeliness of the student's research work, which can ultimately determine students' timely completion (Ungadi, 2021). A positive and supportive relationship between the student and the supervisor can enhance the student's motivation and commitment to completing research work within the stipulated time frame.

On the other hand, a negative relationship can lead to delays, lack of progress, and ultimately, a low timely completion. According to Malunda, Atwebembeire and Ssentamu (2021), the student must communicate effectively with supervisors, ask for help when needed, and be receptive to constructive feedback. The supervisor should also be able to provide timely feedback, encourage the student, and provide the necessary resources to help them complete research work on time irrespective of any impending or ongoing ASUU strike.

The incessant strike actions by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) in Nigeria have become a recurring and deeply entrenched issue in Nigeria's higher education system. These strikes, often characterized by work stoppages and industrial actions, are initiated by ASUU as a means of advocating for improved conditions for academic staff and the overall development of the nation's universities (Saka, 2023). Several factors often contribute to the ASUU strikes, including grievances related to funding, infrastructure, salaries, and the quality of education. According to Ogwuche and Alfa (2023), the incessant strikes by ASUU have significant negative impacts on postgraduate students' timely completion of their programs. These strikes disrupt the academic calendar, create uncertainty, and introduce various challenges that often hinder postgraduate students' progress in several ways. One of such ways is the frequent suspension of academic activities for extended periods (Iwara, Mwale & Simbarashe, 2018). This disrupts the carefully planned academic calendar and can result in programme extensions, delayed coursework, and postponed research activities, all of which can negatively affect timely completion.

Also, when ASUU strikes occur, access to research materials, laboratories, and academic advisors may be limited or temporarily unavailable (Idowu, 2020). These disruptions could cause delays in PG students' data collection, analysis, and the overall research process, extending the time needed to complete the programme. However, ASUU strike may also have some positive effects on postgraduate educational management students' timely completion of their programmes. According to Monogbe and Monogbe (2019), ASUU strikes often revolve around demands for improved infrastructure, better learning resources, and modernized facilities in Nigerian universities. When these strikes lead to negotiations and eventual resolutions,

universities may receive increased funding and resources for infrastructure development. This could create a more conducive environment for all postgraduate students to conduct research, access updated materials, and complete their programmes efficiently. This situation might not be different to postgraduate educational management students in universities in North-East, Nigeria.

Furthermore, postgraduate educational management is an educational programme that is been offered in few universities in North-East, Nigeria with the main purpose of training highly motivated, creative and efficient teachers, school managers and administrators to become Masters and Doctorate in the field. However, there is no specific definition of the aims and objectives of postgraduate studies in Nigeria, rather the aims of higher education were all lumped together in one piece in the 1981 and revised 2013 National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013). This scenario might have far reached implications on postgraduate programmes and that could be the reason behind the elongated duration of courses, frustration, abandonment of programmes by postgraduate students and the ill-prepared graduates from the programmes as observed by the researcher. This situation therefore requires assessing the true state of postgraduate educational management programme and reasons for students' low timely completion. It was therefore against this background that the current study was intended to investigate how student-supervisor relationship and ASUU's strike action determines students' timely completion in Postgraduate Educational Management programme (PGEMP) in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The reality today is that, many Postgraduate Educational Management Programme (PGEMP) students fail to complete their programme within the designated timeframe of 18months for Masters programme and 3years for a PhD programme. The researchers observed that many PGEMP students, struggle to balance several commitments, such as work, family responsibilities, and other personal obligations, in addition to their studies. While some other PGEMP students have limited financial resources and access to necessary research materials, equipment, or software. This may have impacted students' progress and completion time. There are also other students who constantly experience delays in receiving feedback or obtaining necessary support from supervisors, thereby contributing to extended completion times. Previous studies, however, has shown that variation in students' postgraduate degree completion dates is a major problem for all tertiary institution stakeholders (Onuegbu, 2015; Badau, 2020).

The consequences of delayed completion time in PGEMP to students include additional expenses in terms of fees, loss of career opportunity, emotional breakdown, and attrition. Also, the consequences of delayed students' timely completion to lecturers include individual stress from heavy workload, loss of valuable time and resources due to all the training and supervision invested in the candidate. It may also result in possible delay in supervision bonuses and promotion that often comes from producing graduates in their field. Furthermore, the institution suffers income loss, recruitment costs, tuition costs, low student enrolment and output, and, most importantly, failure to generate the necessary human capital for the economy. In addition, the researcher also discovered a scarcity of empirical evidence, particularly in this region and on this phenomenon which created the need for this study. It was based on the aforementioned issues that the researchers investigated how student-supervisor relationship and ASUU's strike action determines timely completion in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to investigate how student-supervisor relationship and ASUU's strike action determines timely completion in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to ascertain how:

1. Student-supervisor relationship in postgraduate educational management programme determines students' timely completion in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.
2. ASUU's strike action in postgraduate educational management programme determines students' timely completion in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent do students relate with their supervisors in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria?
2. To what extent do ASUU strikes impact postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria?
3. What is the timely completion rate in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance:

- H₀₁:** Students-supervisor relationship does not significantly determine Postgraduate Educational Management Programme students' timely completion in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** ASUU strike actions do not significantly determine Postgraduate Educational Management Programme students' timely completion in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study's theoretical framework was anchored on von Bertalanffy's Systems Theory of 1950 and Locke's Goal Setting and Self-Regulation Theory of 1968. The foundation of the systems theory is the idea that all systems (including the galaxy, the planetary system, the social structure, a car, education, the classroom, a child, a plant, an atom, etc.) have various parts that each perform a different function, but in a way that causes them to interact and be dependent on one another as well as on other systems (the environment) around them. As a result, changes to one element of the system have an impact on the other parts as well as the surroundings. On the other hand, Locke's goal setting and self-regulation theory underscores the pivotal role of setting specific and challenging goals in motivating individuals to perform at their best. At the heart of Locke's theory is the idea that individuals are more likely to excel when they have clear and well-defined objectives. Specific goals provide individuals with a clear target to strive for, while challenging goals push them to exert extra effort and engage in a higher level of performance. Overall, adopting systems theory to this study helps to ensure that its application to postgraduate education can help improve the design and implementation of graduate programs. This in turn can help ensure the success of postgraduate students, particularly in graduating on-time. The adoption of this theory will help university management to understand the factors that impact student success and timely completion.

Concept of Postgraduate Educational Management Programme

A postgraduate programme is a programme of study that one can pursue after completing their undergraduate degree. These programmes typically involve more advanced and specialized study in a particular field or subject area. Postgraduate programmes are generally designed to provide students with advanced knowledge, skills, and training that will prepare them for careers in academia, research, industry, or other professional settings. The overall aim of research in postgraduate education is to produce critical thinkers who should be able to evaluate and analyse different types of information gathered in their chosen field of expertise (Ereh & Orji, 2021). According to Agu and Odimegwu (2014), postgraduate education programmes take various forms but generally requires those admitted to such programmes to have completed a bachelor's degree. Consequently, nomenclatures such as postgraduate diploma, Master's degree, Master of Philosophy, PhD or higher PhD are now commonly encountered in tertiary education systems.

Postgraduate education curricula in demand extensive research in the form of an original essay, also known as a thesis or dissertation report, which is a prerequisite for fulfilling the requirements for the award of a postgraduate degree or diploma in all educational programmes. All postgraduate degrees share the ability to pursue further study in a specialist field, and the majority of them call for an undergraduate degree to be considered for admission. Most individual pursue postgraduate degrees for various reasons, such as to enter academia and research or to concentrate in a particular employment path (Fernandez et al., 2019). Enrolling in a graduate school is a significant investment for an individual and requires evaluating both professional and personal long-term goals (Blagg & Blom, 2018; Tran, 2017). Some people decide to get a postgraduate degree in order to completely change their course of study or job. Additionally, postgraduate study offers students the chance to explore and grasp a subject in-depth, and it is well worth the time and money. A postgraduate degree also assists an individual's professional prospects because it shows that the individual is committed to continuing education and possess a greater understanding of a certain field.

A postgraduate educational management programme is a specialized course of study designed for individuals who want to enhance their knowledge and skills in managing educational institutions. It is typically aimed at professionals already working in the field of education or those who aspire to leadership positions in educational organizations. The programme focuses on various aspects of educational management, including organizational leadership, policy development, financial management, curriculum planning, instructional supervision, and assessment strategies. It equips students with the necessary competencies to effectively manage educational institutions and promote quality education. Some key features and benefits of a postgraduate educational management programme include: (a) advanced knowledge: the programme provides an in-depth understanding of educational theories, concepts, and best practices in educational management. Students gain insights into the latest trends and research in the field; (b) leadership skills: the programme emphasizes the development of leadership skills specific to the educational context. Students learn to lead teams, manage resources, and make informed decisions to improve educational outcomes. In addition, (c) policy and governance: students explore the policies and regulations governing educational institutions. They learn how to navigate the legal and ethical aspects of educational management and implement effective governance structures; (d) financial management: the programme covers budgeting, resource allocation, and financial planning in educational settings. Students learn to manage finances efficiently and optimize resource utilization; (e) curriculum development: students gain expertise in designing and evaluating curricula to meet educational goals and standards. They learn strategies for aligning curriculum with learning outcomes and incorporating innovative teaching

methodologies; (f) instructional supervision: the programme focuses on instructional supervision techniques to support teachers and improve teaching practices. Students learn to provide constructive feedback, conduct teacher evaluations, and facilitate professional development; (g) quality assurance and assessment: students explore methods for assessing student learning and ensuring quality education. They learn to design and implement effective assessment strategies, monitor student progress, and use data for continuous improvement. Furthermore, (h) networking opportunities: postgraduate educational management programmes often provide networking opportunities with professionals in the field, including educators, administrators, policymakers, and researchers. These connections can be valuable for career advancement and collaboration; (i) career advancement: a postgraduate educational management programme enhances career prospects and opens doors to leadership positions in educational institutions, such as principal, school administrator, superintendent, or education consultant; and (j) professional development: continuous learning and professional development are crucial in the dynamic field of education. By pursuing a postgraduate program, individuals can stay updated with emerging trends, research, and best practices. Thus, it is important to note that the specific curriculum and requirements of a postgraduate educational management programme may vary among universities and countries. Overall, postgraduate programmes are an important part of higher education, as they provide individuals with the opportunity to pursue advanced study and training in their chosen field, and can lead to increased career opportunities and contributions to the field.

Concept of Timely Completion

Timely completion is generally referred to as the percentage of students who finish their degree programmes within the anticipated time frame. This phrase is additionally known as timely completion. The achievement of any educational objectives depends heavily on students graduating on time. For students, host universities, prospective candidates, and the country at large, on-time graduation is crucial. For instance, a typical Master’s programme would take two years to complete, whereas a typical Doctoral programme might take four to six years. The proportion of students who finish their degree programmes within this anticipated period is measured by the postgraduate timely completion. The percentage of students that finish their degree programme within the anticipated time period is measured by the timely completion (Osaheni, Onyenania & Momoh, 2017). Depending on the sort of degree programme, the anticipated time frame can change, but generally speaking, it is the period of time allotted by the institution for fulfilling the degree requirements.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was used to guide the study. According to Mills (2022), descriptive survey research design refers to a particular type of research design where the primary method of data collection is by survey. The area of the study was North-East, Nigeria. North-East, Nigeria is one of the six geopolitical zone in Nigeria that is made up of six states, namely: Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe States. However, for the purpose of this study, only universities that offers postgraduate (Masters and PhD) programme in Educational Management/Administration and Planning in North-East, Nigeria was selected. These institutions included: Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State; Adamawa State University, Mubi, Adamawa State; Federal University, Kashere, Gombe State and Taraba State University, Jalingo, Taraba State.

The population for the study was 296, which included 21 postgraduate educational management lecturers and 275 postgraduate educational management students from universities offering postgraduate Educational Management/ Administration and Planning programme in North-East, Nigeria. The sample for this study 296, which was selected using census sampling. The instruments that were used to collect data from the respondents were a structured questionnaire and a

checklist. A questionnaire titled: “Postgraduate Educational Management Programme Variable (PEMPVQ), and used to elicit information from PG lecturers and students in PG educational management programme in Universities in North-East, Nigeria. The Checklist on the other hand was titled “PGEMP Completion Rate” and used to determine the completion rate of PGEMP students. The content and face validation of the instruments were carried out by three experts (who are Senior Lecturers and above), in the department of Physical Sciences Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola.

To determine the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted at the Department of Educational Foundations of the University of Jos, Plateau State to 20 respondents (15 students and 5 lecturers) in postgraduate educational management programme in the institution, who are not part of the sampled population. The data collected was then trial tested using Cronbach Alpha statistic to determine the internal consistency of the items. The test showed a reliability co-efficient of 0.811 for PEMPVQ, which meant that the instrument was reliable. Three research assistants were engaged and briefed on how to assist in data collection. At the end of the data collection exercise, 283 valid questionnaires were retrieved, which represent 95.6% of the total questionnaires administered. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while Linear Regression was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The results are presented in the order of research questions 1 – 3 and hypotheses 1 – 2 from Table 1 to Table 5.

Research Question 1: To what extent do supervisors relate with their supervisees in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Extent of Students-Supervisor Relationship in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme in Universities of Universities in North-East, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 283	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	PGEMP supervisors’ physical availability for supervision		3.96	1.06	HE
2.	PGEMP supervisor-student rapport		4.06	1.07	HE
3.	PGEMP supervisor’s openness for online interaction		3.65	1.10	HE
4.	PGEMP supervisor’s constant feedback on thesis		3.95	1.26	HE
5.	Supervisor’s mannerisms during supervision		4.09	1.07	HE
6.	Supervisors’ willingness to provide relevant materials for students		4.02	0.94	HE
7.	PGEMP supervisor’s willingness to assist students with developing research questions		3.93	1.26	HE
8.	Most PGEMP students are comfortable discussing their thesis issues with their supervisors		3.45	1.13	ME
9.	PGEMP supervisors often attend to supervisees outside the University		4.17	0.90	HE
10.	PGEMP supervisors often prioritise appointments with supervisees		3.61	1.05	HE
Grand Mean			3.89		HE

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 1 show the responses of the respondents to research question 1. The table reveals that all the items were at a high extent, except item 48, which was at a moderate extent in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. The table further reveals a grand mean response score of 3.89. This finding implies that students-supervisor relationship is at a high extent in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: To what extent do ASUU strikes impact postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Extent of ASUU strikes in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 283	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
11.	ASUU strikes has caused disruptions in the academic calendar		4.24	1.21	HE
12.	During ASUU strikes, limited access to research materials affects PGEMP students		3.95	1.18	HE
13.	Strikes have resulted in inconsistent PGEMP supervision		3.80	1.34	HE
14.	Postponement of assessments during ASUU strikes affects PGEMP students		4.05	1.26	HE
15.	ASUU strikes often affect PGEMP students' career plans		3.87	1.25	HE
16.	The unpredictability of ASUU strikes often cause psychological stress among PGEMP students		3.89	1.15	HE
17.	ASUU strikes have led to a loss of research momentum, reducing PGEMP students' enthusiasm to their research thesis		3.77	1.42	HE
18.	Administrative inefficiencies following strikes, have affected PGEMP students		3.82	1.29	HE
19.	ASUU strikes have resulted in delays in the availability of academic supervisors		3.98	1.28	HE
20.	ASUU strikes have impacted the quality of education received by PGEMP students		3.63	1.23	HE
Grand Mean			3.78		HE

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 2 shows the responses of the respondents to research question 2. The table reveals that all the items were at a high extent in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. The table further reveals a grand mean response score of 3.90. This finding implies that the extent of ASUU strikes in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria is at a high extent.

Research Question 3: What is the timely completion rate in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria?

Table 3: Checklist of Students' Timely Completion Rate in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria

Programme	University	Students Enrol	EYG	AYG	NoG	Decision	
						T	NT
Masters' PGEMP in Universities in North East Nigeria	MAU, Yola 2019-20	30	2020-21	2020-21	-	-	√
				2021-22	4	-	√
				2022-23	15	-	√
	TSU, Jalingo 2019-20	43	2020-21	2020-21	-	-	√
				2021-22	12	-	√
				2022-23	14	-	√
	FU, Kashere 2020-21	27	2021-22	2021-22	-	-	√
				2022-23	18	-	√
				2021-22	-	-	√
	ADSU, Mubi 2020-21	7	2021-22	2021-22	-	-	√
2022-23				3	-	√	
Total MEd		107	-	-	66	-	66

PhD PGEMP in Universities in North East Nigeria	MAU, Yola 2019-20	8	2022-23	2022-23	2	√	-
				2023-24	-	-	-
	TSU, Jalingo 2019-20	9	2022-23	2022-23	2	√	-
				2023-24	-	-	-
	FU, Kashere	-	-	-	-	-	-
	ADSU, Mubi	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Total PhD	17	-	-	4	4	-
OVERALL TOTAL		124		-	70	4	66
MEAN SCORE							1.0571
STANDARD DEVIATION							0.23379

KEY: EYG = Expected Year of Graduation; NoG = Number of Graduates;
 AYG = Actual Year of Graduation; T = Timely; UT = Untimely

Table 3 shows the checklist result of 2019/2020 and 2020/2021 PGEMP students' timely completion rate in universities in North East, Nigeria. The checklist further revealed that only four PG students completed their programme on time out of the total 70 PGEMP students that graduated during the session examined (2019-20/2020-19 academic session). The table further revealed a mean score for timely completion to be 1.06 with a standard deviation of 0.22 in PGEMP in universities in North-East, Nigeria.

Hypotheses Testing

The null hypotheses were tested using Linear and Multiple Regression Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the following acronym stands: df = degree of freedom; r = correlation co-efficient and sig = level of significance.

Ho: Students-supervisor relationship does not significantly determine Postgraduate Educational Management Programme Students' timely completion in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.

Table 4a: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of how Students-Supervisor Relationship determines Students' Timely Completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.562	1	.562	11.902	.001 ^b
	Residual	3.210	281	.047		
	Total	3.771	282			

a. Dependent Variable: Timely Completion

b. Predictors: (Constant), Students-Supervisor Relationship

The results of analysis in Table 4a presents analysis of variance (ANOVA) of linear regression analysis that aims to examine how students-supervisor relationship determines students' timely completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. The result reveals that students-supervisor relationship significantly determines timely completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 281) = 11.902, p < 0.05$. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected since the p – value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4b: Model Summary of how Students-Supervisor Relationship determines Students’ Timely Completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.386 ^a	.149	.136	.21726

a. Predictors: (Constant), Students-Supervisor Relationship

Table 4b shows a model summary that demonstrates how the independent variable accounts for the variance in the dependent variable and the strength of the determinants. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) is a measure of how well the independent variable(s) (students-supervisor relationship) explain the variance in the dependent variable (timely completion). The results reveal that 13.6% of the variation in timely completion could be attributed to students-supervisor relationship. The results also show that students-supervisor relationship significantly determines students’ timely completion as indicated by the r-value of 0.386.

H02: ASUU strike actions do not significantly determine Postgraduate Educational Management Programme students’ timely completion in Universities of North-East, Nigeria.

Table 5a: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of how ASUU strike actions determine Students’ Timely Completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.374	1	.374	7.494	.008 ^b
	Residual	3.397	281	.050		
	Total	3.771	282			

a. Dependent Variable: Timely Completion

b. Predictors: (Constant), ASUU strike actions

The results of analysis in Table 5a presents analysis of variance (ANOVA) of linear regression analysis that aims to examine how ASUU strikes determines students’ timely completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. The result reveals that ASUU strikes significantly determines timely completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme in Universities of North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 281) = 7.494, p < 0.05$. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected since the p – value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5b: Model Summary of how ASUU strikes determines Students’ Timely Completion in Postgraduate Educational Management Programme

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.315 ^a	.099	.086	.22351

a. Predictors: (Constant), ASUU strikes

Table 5b shows a model summary that demonstrates how the independent variable accounts for the variance in the dependent variable and the strength of the determinants. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) is a measure of how well the independent variable(s) (ASUU strikes) explain the variance in the dependent variable (timely completion). The results reveal that 8.6% of the variation in timely completion could be attributed to ASUU strikes. The results also show that ASUU strikes significantly determines students’ timely completion as indicated by the r-value of 0.315.

DISCUSSION

The study also found in Table 1 that students-supervisor relationship in PGEMP in Universities of North-East, Nigeria is at a high extent, with a grand mean of 3.89. This finding concurred with Malunda, Atwebembeire and Ssentamu (2021); Saleem and Mahmood (2017); Ali, Watson and Dhingra's (2016) findings that supervisor-supervisee relationship, supervisor guidance and feedback are high antecedents of the graduate students' progression. Nevertheless, Ndayambaje (2018) study revealed that there is often a limited level of supervisor-supervisee interaction in postgraduate programmes, which disagrees with the study's finding. Jeyaraj's (2020) study also disagrees as it revealed that there is a low extent of postgraduate students-supervisor interaction. The implication of the study's finding is that it suggests that when supervisors provide adequate support, feedback, and encouragement to students, through high interaction, it thereby helps enhance students' learning experience and research outcomes. Additionally, a positive supervisor-student relationship can contribute to students' professional development, networking opportunities, and overall well-being during their academic journey.

However, hypothesis 1 was rejected, as the results showed that students-supervisor relationship significantly determines timely completion in PGEMP in Universities of North-East, Nigeria, with $F(1, 281) = 11.902, p < 0.05$. The finding was in line with Saleem and Mahmood (2017) result, which yielded a positive and high significant correlation between students-supervisor relationship and students' early completion. Also, Priyadarshini, Gurnam, Teoh, Geethanjali and Chan (2022) finding shows that students-supervisor level of interaction significantly influenced postgraduate students' motivation to GOT. However, Kondo, Heitz-Tokpa, Bonfoh and Akindes (2022) finding disagree with hypothesis 1 finding as it showed that supervisors' styles and rapport but has no significant impact on students' graduation. Thus, the implication of the significant determinant of students-supervisor relationship underscores the critical role that mentorship and guidance from supervisors play in supporting students' progress towards timely completion. A positive and supportive relationship between students and their supervisors fosters effective communication, collaboration, and feedback exchange, which are essential for navigating the complexities of postgraduate research and completing academic requirements in a timely manner. When students feel valued, respected, and supported by their supervisors, they are more likely to stay motivated, focused, and on track towards graduation.

The study also found in Table 2 that ASUU strikes in PGEMP in Universities of North-East, Nigeria is at a high extent, with a grand mean of 3.90. The high extent of incessant ASUU (Academic Staff Union of Universities) strikes indicates a significant challenge facing postgraduate educational management programmes in Universities of North-East, Nigeria. ASUU strikes disrupt academic activities, delay programme timelines, and negatively impact students' learning experiences and academic progress. These strikes often stem from issues such as funding, infrastructure, working conditions, and academic autonomy. This finding concurred with Idowu (2020); Monogbe and Monogbe (2019); Ogwuche and Alfa (2023) findings that ASUU strikes has relatively become a norm in the Nigerian's educational system. Although, Chukwudi and Idowu (2021) study discovered that the strikes are orchestrated largely by the union quest to protect its members' welfare and swift greeting of any perceived unfriendly steps by the government with strike actions while the government fell short in funding and entrenching a right legal milieu for negotiation and regulation of ASUU. However, the implication of the study's finding is that addressing the underlying causes of ASUU strikes is essential as it is recognised as being a common challenge to PGEMP.

In addition, hypothesis 2 was rejected, as the results showed that ASUU strikes significantly determines timely completion in PGEMP in Universities of North-East, Nigeria, with $F(1, 281) = 7.494, p < 0.05$. The finding was in line with Idowu (2020) hypothesis finding that there were no significant differences in the perception of lecturers and students, that

incessant strikes impact negatively on students' academic performance. Also, Monogbe and Monogbe (2019) study reveal that quality of education and student performance is negatively influenced by incessant ASUU strike. The implication of the significant determinant of ASUU strikes underscores the disruptive impact of labour strikes on students' progress towards timely completion of their postgraduate educational management programmes. ASUU strikes disrupt academic activities, delay programme timelines, and negatively impact students' learning experiences and academic progress. These strikes often stem from issues such as funding, infrastructure, working conditions, and academic autonomy. The finding highlights the urgent need for institutions and stakeholders to address the underlying causes of labour strikes and implement lasting solutions to minimize their impact on students' academic pursuits.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the study concludes that student-supervisor relationship and ASUU's strike action determine students' timely completion in postgraduate educational management programme in Universities of North-East Nigeria. These findings underscore the importance of adopting a comprehensive and holistic student support approach to postgraduate programme management. Hence, institutions must remain proactive in identifying student-supervisor relationship areas for enhancement and implementing targeted interventions to support PG students' progress towards timely completion.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends the following:

1. PGEMP supervisors should facilitate meaningful interactions and communication between students and themselves. They can provide opportunities for regular feedback, guidance, and support to enhance the quality of supervision.
2. The University management and respective stakeholders in PGEMP should develop contingency plans and alternative instructional methods to minimize disruptions caused by ASUU strikes. They can advocate for policies and resources that support higher education and address underlying issues contributing to ASUU strikes.
3. The University management, especially the School of Postgraduate Studies and stakeholders in PGEMP should establish mechanisms for ongoing monitoring and evaluation of programme determinants and their impact on students' timely completion. They can use data-driven insights to identify areas for improvement and inform decision-making processes.

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